

ARTS

GENEVA'S URBAN GREEN SPACES: A MODEL FOR LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN INTEGRATION IN YEREVAN

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Abstract

This article presents an in-depth exploration of Geneva's urban landscape architecture, based on on-site observations conducted in August 2024. It examines the historical development, design principles, and architectural features of Geneva's parks and gardens, emphasizing their multifunctional role in urban life. The research identifies key elements, such as sustainability, accessibility, and cultural integration, which contribute to Geneva's reputation as one of Europe's greenest cities. Furthermore, the findings are proposed as a model for modernizing Yerevan's parks, with specific applications in water conservation, multifunctional space design, and the incorporation of local cultural elements.

Keywords: Geneva, Yerevan, landscape, architecture, urban design, urban planning.

Introduction

In the 21st century, cities face the dual challenge of providing livable spaces while responding to ecological concerns. Urban parks and green spaces have emerged as vital to this effort, offering environmental benefits while improving the quality of life for residents. Geneva, Switzerland, stands as a shining example of how a city can integrate green spaces into its urban fabric. Based on my detailed on-site observations in August 2024, this article explores the design, historical development, and architectural significance of Geneva's parks and gardens. These findings will be applied to future projects in Yerevan, Armenia, to modernize its parks and address challenges unique to the region.

Despite Geneva's rich history of urban landscape development, there has been little academic focus on the specific architectural and design strategies employed in its parks. This study addresses this gap and highlights Geneva as a case study for landscape design that can inspire improvements in other cities.

Methodology

The observations conducted in Geneva were part of a comprehensive, qualitative study aimed at understanding how the city's parks and gardens are designed and utilized. The methodology involved a combination of walking surveys, photography, mapping, and structured observations. Over the course of August, I visited more than 10 parks, taking detailed notes on spatial layouts, design elements, accessibility features, and the integration of natural resources. Additionally, I interviewed local landscape architects and park managers to gather insights into the historical development and design philosophy behind these spaces.

This on-the-ground approach allowed me to assess not only the aesthetic aspects of the parks but also their functionality, sustainability, and role within the broader urban ecosystem. These observations will directly inform the modernization of Yerevan's parks by integrating sustainable, user-centered, and culturally appropriate design elements.

Historical Development of Geneva's Green Spaces

Geneva's urban park system has evolved over centuries, reflecting various historical periods and design philosophies. The first significant developments in Geneva's public parks began after the city's fortifications were dismantled in the mid-19th century. The removal of these walls enabled urban expansion and the creation of green spaces that would serve the growing population. Parc des Bastions, established in 1817, is a prime example of this early development. Designed as a public promenade, it became a place for intellectual exchange, with sculptures and monuments paying homage to Geneva's role in the Enlightenment.

By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Geneva's green spaces began to reflect broader European trends in landscape design. The rise of the English garden movement introduced a more naturalistic style, characterized by meandering paths, sweeping lawns, and informal groupings of trees. This is particularly evident in parks like Jardin Anglais, which diverges from the structured formality of earlier French-inspired designs. As Geneva grew in prominence as an international hub, its parks became cultural symbols as well as recreational spaces.

Geneva Botanical Garden: A Blend of Science and Landscape Art

The Geneva Botanical Garden, established in 1817, serves as one of the city's most significant contributions to botanical research and landscape design. Located near Lake Geneva, this 28-hectare garden is both a scientific institution and a public park. It houses over 16,000 species of plants, representing diverse climates and ecosystems from around the world. The garden's mission is twofold: promoting botanical knowledge and preserving biodiversity.

Architecturally, the Botanical Garden is designed to blend function with beauty. Its layout features themed sections, such as a rock garden, arboretum, and medicinal plant garden, each carefully arranged to create a sense of harmony between natural and designed elements. In addition to outdoor gardens, the site includes greenhouses that replicate tropical and subtropical climates, showcasing exotic plant species that cannot survive Geneva's temperate climate.

The Japanese garden, one of the most popular sections, highlights Geneva's embrace of international landscape design traditions. Its calm, minimalist design contrasts with the more intricate flower beds and perennial gardens found elsewhere in the park. Through its educational and aesthetic design, the Geneva Botanical Garden demonstrates how green spaces can serve multiple purposes—scientific research, conservation, recreation, and cultural engagement.

This multi-purpose design approach is something I intend to apply in Yerevan, where parks could serve not only as recreational spaces but also as cultural and educational hubs. The integration of botanical elements, combined with water-efficient landscapes tailored to Yerevan's dry climate, would foster greater public engagement with nature while promoting environmental sustainability.

Architectural and Landscape Design of Geneva's Parks

Geneva's parks reflect a thoughtful blend of local heritage and international influences. Each park is tailored to its environment, showcasing the city's ability to harmonize nature with urban life. Key architectural and design features observed during my research include:

1. Spatial Organization and Connectivity

One of Geneva's most remarkable achievements is the seamless connection between its parks and the broader urban network. Pedestrian walkways, cycling paths, and public transportation routes are all intricately linked to the city's green spaces. Parc des Bastions, for instance, is directly adjacent to Geneva's university district, making it a central meeting point for students, tourists, and residents alike.

2. Formal vs. Informal Designs

Geneva's parks exhibit a mix of formal and informal designs. Formal designs, such as those in Parc La Perle du Lac, employ classical European styles with symmetrical layouts, manicured lawns, and ornamental fountains. On the other hand, parks like Bois de la Bâtie embrace a more naturalistic, forest-like atmosphere, with winding paths and unstructured greenery. This diversity in design provides users with different experiences, from serene reflection to active engagement with nature.

3. Integration of Art and Nature

Public art plays a significant role in many of Geneva's parks. Monuments, sculptures, and historical markers enrich the visual landscape while adding layers of cultural meaning. Parc des Bastions is home to the famous Reformation Wall, a monumental tribute to key figures of the Protestant Reformation. Meanwhile, the giant chessboards scattered throughout the park invite public interaction, blurring the lines between art and recreation.

4. Sustainable Design Practices

Sustainability is a guiding principle in Geneva's park management. Many parks are designed to promote biodiversity and reduce water usage. Native plants, for example, are chosen for their adaptability to the local climate, reducing the need for excessive irrigation. Parks like Parc Bertrand and Parc de la Grange incorporate low-maintenance greenery and efficient water management systems, reflecting Geneva's commitment to ecological

responsibility. These sustainability practices could be highly relevant in Yerevan, where water conservation is a pressing issue.

Observations and Novelty of Research

During my 2 week observation, several key findings emerged that set Geneva apart from other European cities in terms of landscape architecture:

1. Multifunctional Design

Geneva's parks are not merely recreational spaces; they are multifunctional environments that serve cultural, social, and ecological purposes. Parks like Parc de la Grange host concerts and community events, while others, such as Parc Mon Repos, integrate historical landmarks with leisure spaces.

2. Accessibility and Inclusivity

Geneva's parks are designed with inclusivity in mind, offering facilities for people of all ages and abilities. Playgrounds, fitness areas, and shaded seating areas cater to families, while wide pathways accommodate wheelchairs and strollers. This emphasis on accessibility is a principle that will be incorporated into Yerevan's park redesigns, ensuring that green spaces are welcoming to all residents.

3. Seasonality and Year-Round Use

Geneva's parks are designed to be functional and aesthetically pleasing throughout the year. The city's landscape architects have carefully selected plants that offer visual interest in all seasons, from the lush greenery of summer to the structural beauty of evergreen trees in winter. Seasonal flower displays, like those in Parc des Eaux-Vives, attract visitors during warmer months, while parks like Parc Bertrand remain lively year-round due to their varied plant life and open spaces.

Application to Yerevan: A Vision for Green Urban Renewal

Yerevan's urban development has historically focused on monumental architecture, with less emphasis on public green spaces. As the city grows, the need for well-designed, functional parks is becoming more apparent. The insights gathered from Geneva offer several key lessons for Yerevan's future urban renewal projects:

1. Water Conservation and Drought-Resistant Landscaping

Geneva's use of native plants and efficient irrigation systems can serve as a model for Yerevan, where water resources are limited. By prioritizing drought-resistant species and low-maintenance landscapes, Yerevan's parks can remain green and inviting despite the city's arid climate.

2. Cultural Integration

Just as Geneva's parks celebrate the city's history and international character, Yerevan's green spaces could incorporate Armenian cultural and historical elements. Public art installations, historical monuments, and themed gardens could transform Yerevan's parks into spaces that reflect the city's rich cultural heritage.

3. Multi-Use Spaces for a Growing City

Yerevan, like Geneva, can benefit from creating multifunctional parks that serve both recreational and cultural purposes. Spaces for concerts, outdoor markets, and educational workshops could enhance the social value of Yerevan's parks, making them more than just places for relaxation.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significance of Geneva’s landscape architecture and its potential as a model for other cities, including Yerevan. Through the integration of well-designed, accessible, and sustainable green spaces, Geneva has successfully created an urban environment that promotes public health, cultural engagement, and environmental sustainability. The findings

from this research emphasize the critical role green spaces play in shaping not only the physical landscape of a city but also its social and cultural identity. By applying Geneva’s innovative landscape practices, Yerevan can evolve into a more resilient, inclusive, and ecologically balanced urban space.

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